

Secondary k-column symmetric Neutrosophic Fuzzy Matrices

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Abstract: Objective: The objective of this study is to establish the results of secondary k- column symmetric (CS) Neutrosophic fuzzy matrices. **Methods and Findings:** We have applied CS condition in neutrosophic environment to find the relation between s-k CS, s- CS, k- CS and CS. **Novelty:** We establish the necessary and sufficient criteria for s-k CS Neutrosophic fuzzy matrices and various g-inverses of an s – k CS Neutrosophic fuzzy matrices to be an s – k CS. The generalized inverses of an s – k CS P corresponding to the sets $P\{1, 2\}$, $P\{1, 2, 3\}$ and $P\{1, 2, 4\}$ are characterized.

Keywords: Neutrosophic fuzzy matrices (NFM), s-column symmetric, k-column symmetric, column symmetric.

1. Introduction

Zadeh [1] has studied fuzzy set (FS). Atanassov [2] introduced intuitionistic FSs. Smarandache [3] has discussed the concept of neutrosophic sets. Khan, Shyamal, and Pal [4] have studied intuitionistic fuzzy matrices (IFMs) for the first time. Atanassov [5,6] has discussed IFS and Operations over IV IFS. Hashimoto [7] has studied Canonical form of a transitive matrix. Kim and Roush [8] have studied generalized fuzzy matrices. Lee [9] has studied Secondary Skew Symmetric, Secondary Orthogonal Matrices. Hill and Waters [10] have analyzed On k-Real and k-Hermitian matrices. Meenakshi [11] has studied Fuzzy Matrix: Theory and Applications.

Anandhkumar [12,13] has studied Pseudo Similarity of NFM and On various Inverse of NFM. Punithavalli and Anandhkumar [14] have studied Reverse Sharp and Left-T And Right- T Partial Ordering on IFM. Pal and Susanta Kha [15] have studied IV Intuitionistic Fuzzy Matrices. Vidhya and Irene Hepzibah [16] have discussed on Interval Valued NFM. Anandhkumar et.al [17,18] has focused on Reverse Sharp and Left-T Right-T Partial Ordering on NFM and IFM. Anandhkumar,et.al have studied [19] Partial orderings, Characterizations and Generalization of k-idempotent NFM. Here, we introduce the Secondary k-CS NFM and introduce some basic operators on NFMs.

1.1 Literature Review

Meenakshi and Jaya Shree [20] have studied On k-kernel symmetric matrices. Meenakshi and Krishnamoorthy [21] have characterized On Secondary k-Hermitian matrices. Meenakshi and Jaya Shree [22] have studied On k -range symmetric matrices. Jaya shree [23] has studied Secondary κ -Kernel Symmetric Fuzzy Matrices. Shyamal and Pal [24] Interval valued Fuzzy matrices. Meenakshi and Kalliraja [25] have studied Regular Interval valued Fuzzy matrices. Anandhkumar [26] has studied Kernal and k-kernal Intuitionistic Fuzzy matrices. Jaya Shree [27] has discussed Secondary κ -range symmetric fuzzy matrices. Anandhkumar et.al.,[28] have studied Generalized Symmetric NFM. Kaliraja and Bhavani [29] have studied Interval Valued Secondary κ -Range Symmetric Fuzzy Matrices,

Let P be any fuzzy matrix, $P^\dagger$ occurs then this will coincides with the transpose of the matrix (P^T). The fuzzy matrix P belongs to Fn is known to be kernel symmetric matrix, then this shows that $N(P) = N(P^T)$ which does not implies $R[P] = R[P^T]$. But the converse is true. Symmetric matrices are established in the field of complex entries for the theory of k - hermitian matrices. This idea make use of the development of k - EP matrices in the generalization of k - hermitian matrices and also EP matrices. Hill and Waters [30] have initiated the study on κ - real and κ - Hermitian matrices. The concept of Theorems on products of EPr matrices introduced by Baskett and Katz [30]. It is commonly known that for complex matrices, the concepts of range and kernel symmetric are equivalent. But this is fails for Interval valued fuzzy matrices.

The concept of interval valued s - k Hermitian and interval valued kernel symmetric matrices for fuzzy matrices. We also expanded many basic conclusions on these two types of matrices. An Interval valued secondary s - k kernel symmetric fuzzy matrix can be described. Suitable standards for determining g - inverses of an Interval valued secondary s - k - kernel symmetric fuzzy matrices are interval valued secondary s - k - kernel symmetric are found. We establish the necessary and sufficient canditions for an interval valued s - k kernel symmetric fuzzy matrices. Meenakshi, Krishnamoorthy and Ramesh [31] have studied on s - k - EP matrices. Meenakshi and Krishnamoorthy [32] have introduced the idea of s - k hermitian matrices.

Shyamal and Pal [33] have studied Interval valued Fuzzy matrices. The definition of k-symmetric matrices was introduced by the following authors Ann Lec [34] has studied Secondary symmetric and skew symmetric secondary orthogonal matrices. . Anandhkumar et.al [35] have discussed Interval Valued Secondary k-Range Symmetric NFM.

Table:1 Extension of Neutrosophic Fuzzy Matrices based on previous works

References	Extension of Neutrosophic Fuzzy Matrices from Fuzzy Matrices	Year
[20]	On k-kernel symmetric matrices	2009
[22]	On k -range symmetric matrices	2009
[23]	Secondary k-Kernel Symmetric Fuzzy Matrices	2014
[27]	Secondary k-range symmetric FM	2018
[29]	Interval Valued Secondary κ -Range Symmetric Fuzzy Matrices	2022
Proposed	Secondary k-column symmetric Neutrosophic Fuzzy Matrices	2023

From Table 1 and process flow, it is observed that the previous studies are on k-Kernel, K-range, Secondary k-Kernel and Secondary k- range using fuzzy matrices. It is evident that there is a research gap of these studies in Neutrosophic environment. So, based on the above observation, we have established the results of K-column and Secondary k- column in neutrosophic fuzzy matrices.

Notations:

P^T = Transpose of the matrix P

P^+ = Moore-penrose inverse of P

CS = Column symmetric

$C(P)$ = Column space of P

2. Generalized Symmetric NFM

Definition: 2.1 Let P be a NFM, if $C[P] = C[P^T]$ then P is said to be CS.

Example:2.1 Let us consider $P = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.3, 0.5, 0.4 \rangle & \langle 0, 0, 1 \rangle & \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle \\ \langle 0, 0, 1 \rangle & \langle 0, 0, 1 \rangle & \langle 0, 0, 1 \rangle \\ \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle & \langle 0, 0, 1 \rangle & \langle 0.3, 0.2, 0.4 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$,

The following NFM are not CS

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}, P^T = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle^T \in C(P), \quad \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle^T \notin C(P^T)$$

$$\langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle^T \in C(P), \quad \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle^T \in C(P^T)$$

$$\langle 0,0,1 \rangle \ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle^T \in C(P), \quad \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle^T \in C(P^T)$$

$$C(P) \neq C(P^T)$$

Definition 2.2: A NFM $P \in F_n$ is s-symmetric NFM $\Leftrightarrow P = VP^T V$.

Example:2.2 Let us consider $P = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.4,0.3,0.2 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.4,0.3 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \\ \langle 0.5,0.4,0.3 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0.3,0.2,0.4 \rangle \end{bmatrix},$

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

Definition 2.3: A NFM $P \in F_n$ is s-CS NFM $\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(VP^T V)$.

Example:2.3 Let us consider $P = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.7,0.4,0.5 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0.8,0.2,0.1 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle \\ \langle 0.8,0.2,0.1 \rangle & \langle 0,0,1 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.7,0.3 \rangle \end{bmatrix},$

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

Definition 2.4: A NFM $P \in F_n$ is s-k-CS NFM $\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$.

Example:2.4 Let us consider $P = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.7,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle \\ \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.7,0.3,0.5 \rangle \end{bmatrix},$

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}, V = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix},$$

Preliminary: 2.1 Let V is a permutation NFM its satisfies the conditions

- (i) $VV^T = V^T V = I_n$
- (ii) $V^T = V$
- (iii) $C(P) = C(VP)$
- (iv) $C(P) = C(KP)$.

Remark 2.1: We notice that $P = KVP^T VK$ implies that $C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$

This is illustrating the following example

Example 2.5. Consider a NFM, $V = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$,

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.7,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle \\ \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.7,0.3,0.5 \rangle \end{bmatrix}, K = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix},$$

$$KVP^T VK = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.7,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle \\ \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.7,0.3,0.5 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$KVP^T VK = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.7,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle \\ \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.7,0.3,0.5 \rangle \end{bmatrix} = P$$

Therefore, $C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$

Example 2.6. Consider a NFM

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}, V = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0.4,0.2,0.6 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.3,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$KV = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$KV = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$VK = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$VK = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P^T VK = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.5,0.8,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.4,0.8,0.6 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0.4 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0.7,0 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.7,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0.7,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$KVP^T VK = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 1,1,0 \rangle \\ \langle 1,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle & \langle 0,1,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0.5,0.8,0.4 \rangle & \langle 0.4,0.8,0.6 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0.4 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0.7,0 \rangle & \langle 0.5,0.7,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0.7,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$KVP^T VK = \begin{bmatrix} \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0.2,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle & \langle 1,0,0 \rangle \\ \langle 0.5,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0.4,0,0 \rangle & \langle 0,0,0 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \neq P$$

$P \neq KVP^T VK$ is not s- κ -symmetric iff not s- κ -CS.

Theorem 2.1: For NFM $P \in F_n$, the subsequent are equivalent :

- (i) $C(P) = C(P^T)$.
- (ii) $P^T = PH = KP$ for several IFM H, K and $\rho(P) = r$.

Lemma 2.1: For NFM $P \in F_n$ and a PM $K, C(P) = C(Q)$ iff $C(KPK^T) = C(KQK^T)$

Theorem 2.2. For NFM $P \in F_n$ the subsequent are equivalent

- (i) $C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$
- (ii) $C(KVP) = C((KVP)^T)$
- (iii) $C(PKV) = C((PKV)^T)$
- (iv) $C(VP) = C(K(VP)^T K)$
- (v) $C(PK) = C(V(PK)^T V)$

(vi) $C(P^T) = C(KV(P)VK)$

(vii) $C(P) = C(P^T VK)$

(viii) $C(P^T) = C(PKV)$

(ix) $P = VKP^T VKH_1$ for $H_1 \in F_n$

(x) $P = H_1 KVP^T VK$ for $H_1 \in F_n$

(xi) $P^T = KVPVKH$ for $H \in F_n$

(xii) $P^T = HKVPKV$ for $H \in F_n$

Proof: (i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iv)

$\Leftrightarrow P$ is s - κ - CS

$\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$

$\Leftrightarrow C(KVP) = C((KVP)^T)$ [Preliminary 2.1]

$\Leftrightarrow KVP$ is Column symmetric

$\Leftrightarrow VP$ is κ - Column symmetric

So, (i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iv) hence.

(i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (v)

P is s - κ - CS

$\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$ [By Definition 2.4]

$\Leftrightarrow C(KVP) = C((KVP)^T)$ [Preliminary 2.1]

$\Leftrightarrow C(PKV) = C((PKV)^T)$

$\Leftrightarrow PKV$ is Column symmetric

$\Leftrightarrow PK$ is s - Column symmetric

So, (i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (v) hence.

(ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (vii)

KVP is Column symmetric $\Leftrightarrow C(KVP) = C((KVP)^T)$

$\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C((KVP)^T)$ [Preliminary 2.1]

$\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(P^T VK)$

So, (ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (vii) hence.

(iii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (viii):

PVK is Column symmetric $\Leftrightarrow C(PVK) = C((PVK)^T)$

$\Leftrightarrow C(PVK) = C(P^T)$ [Preliminary 2.1]

So, (iii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (viii) hence.

(i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (vi)

P is s- κ - Column symmetric $\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$

$\Leftrightarrow C(KVP) = C((KVP)^T)$ [Preliminary 2.1]

$\Leftrightarrow (KVP)^T$ is Column symmetric

$\Leftrightarrow P^T VK$ is Column symmetric

$\Leftrightarrow P^T$ is s- κ - Column symmetric

So, (i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (vi) hence.

(i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (xi) $\Leftrightarrow$ (x)

P is s- κ - Column symmetric $\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(KVP^T VK)$

$\Leftrightarrow C(P^T) = C(KVPVK)$

$\Leftrightarrow P^T = KVPVKH$ [By Theorem 2.1]

$\Leftrightarrow P = H_1 KV P^T VK$ for $H_1 \in F_n$

So, (i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (xi) $\Leftrightarrow$ (x) hence.

(ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (xii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (ix)

KVP is Column symmetric $\Leftrightarrow VP$ is κ - Column symmetric

$\Leftrightarrow C(VP) = C(K(VP)^T K)$

$\Leftrightarrow C(P) = C(P^T VK)$ [Preliminary 2.1]

$\Leftrightarrow C(P^T) = C(KVP)$

$\Leftrightarrow P^T = HKVP$ for $H \in F_n$ [By Theorem 2.1]

$\Leftrightarrow P^T = HKVPKV$

$$\Leftrightarrow P = VKP^T VKH_1 \text{ for } H_1 \in F_n$$

So, (ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (xii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (ix) hence.

Corollary 2.1: For NFM $P \in F_n$ the subsequent are equivalent:

$$(i) \quad C(P) = C(VP^T V)$$

$$(ii) \quad C(VP) = C(VP)^T$$

$$(iii) \quad C(PV) = C(PV)^T$$

$$(iv) \quad P \text{ is s-CS}$$

$$(v) \quad C(P^T) = C(VPV)$$

$$(vi) \quad C(P) = C(P^T V)$$

$$(vii) \quad C(P^T) = C(PV)$$

$$(viii) \quad C(KVP) = C((VP)^T)$$

$$(ix) \quad P = VP^T VH_1 \text{ for } H_1 \in F_n$$

$$(x) \quad P = H_1 VP^T V \text{ for } H_1 \in F_n$$

$$(xi) \quad P^T = VPVH \text{ for } H \in F_n$$

$$(xii) \quad P^T = HVPV \text{ for } H \in F$$

Theorem 2.3: For NFM $P \in F_n$. Then any two of the subsequent imply the other one:

$$(i) \quad C(P) = C(KP^T K)$$

$$(ii) \quad C(P) = C(VKP^T KV)$$

$$(iii) \quad C(P^T) = C((VKP)^T)$$

Proof: (i) & (ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iii)

P is s- κ -Cs

$$\Rightarrow C(P) = C(P^T VK)$$

$$\Rightarrow C(KPK) = C(KP^T K)$$

[By Lemma 2.1]

Hence (i) & (ii) $\Rightarrow C(P^T) = C((VPK)^T)$

So,(iii) hence.

(i) & (iii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (ii)

P is κ - Column symmetric $\Rightarrow C(P) = C(KP^TK)$

$\Rightarrow C(KPK) = C(P^T)$ [By Lemma 2.1]

Hence (i) & (iii)

$\Rightarrow C(KPK) = C((VPK)^T)$

$\Rightarrow C(P) = C(P^TVK)$

$\Rightarrow C(P) = C(KVP^T)$

$\Rightarrow P$ is s- κ CS [By Theorem 2.2]

So, (ii) hence.

(iii) & (ii) implies (i)

P is s- κ - Cs

$\Rightarrow C(P) = C(P^TVK)$

$\Rightarrow C(KPK) = C(KP^TV)$ [Preliminary 2.1]

Hence (ii) & (iii) $\Rightarrow C(KPK) = C(P^T)$

$\Rightarrow C(P) = C(KP^TK)$ [By Lemma 2.1]

$\Rightarrow P$ is κ - Column symmetric

Therefore,(i) hold. Hence the Theorem

3.s- κ -Column Symmetric Regular NFM

In this section, it was discovered that there are various generalized inverses of matrices in NFM. The comparable standards for different g-inverses of s-k CS NFM to be s-k CS are also established. The generalized inverses of an s - κ CS P corresponding to the sets P{1, 2}, P{1, 2, 3} and P{1, 2, 4} are characterized.

Theorem 3.1: Let $P \in F_n, Z \in P\{1,2\}$ and PZ, ZP, are s- κ -CS NFM. Then P is s- κ - CS NFM $\Leftrightarrow Z$ is s- κ - CS NFM.

Proof: $C(KVP) = C(KVPZP) \subseteq C(ZP)$ [since P = PZP]

$= C(ZVVP) = N(ZVKKVP) \subseteq C(KVP)$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Hence, } C(KVP) &= C(ZP) \\
&= C(KV(ZP)^T VK) \\
&= C(P^T Z^T VK) \\
&= C(Z^T VK) \\
&= C((KVZ)^T) \\
C((KVP)^T) &= C(P^T VK) \\
&= C(Z^T P^T VK) \\
&= C((KVPZ)^T) \\
&= C(KVPZ) \\
&= C(KVZ)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
KVZ \text{ is column symmetric} &\Leftrightarrow C(KVP) = N((KVP)^T) \\
&\Leftrightarrow C((KVZ)^T) = N(KVZ) \\
&\Leftrightarrow KVZ \text{ is CS} \\
&\Leftrightarrow Z \text{ is } s\text{-}\kappa\text{-CS}
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.2: Let $P \in F_n$, $Z \in P\{1,2,3\}$, $C(KVP) = C((KVZ)^T)$. Then P is $s\text{-}\kappa\text{-CS NFM} \Leftrightarrow Z$ is $s\text{-}\kappa\text{-CS NFM}$.

Proof: Given $Z \in P\{1,2,3\}$, we have $PZP = P, ZPZ = Z, (PZ)^T = PZ$

$$\begin{aligned}
C((KVP)^T) &= C(Z^T P^T VK) && \text{[By using } PZP = P\text{]} \\
&= C(KV(PZ)^T) \\
&= C((PZ)^T) && \text{[Preliminary 2.1]} \\
&= C(PZ) && \text{[(PZ)^T = PZ]} \\
&= C(Z) && \text{[By using } Z = ZPZ\text{]} \\
&= C(KVZ) && \text{[Preliminary 2.1]}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
KVP \text{ is column symmetric NFM} &\Leftrightarrow C(KVP) = C((KVP)^T) \\
&\Leftrightarrow C((KVZ)^T) = C(KVZ) \\
&\Leftrightarrow KVZ \text{ is column symmetric} \\
&\Leftrightarrow Z \text{ is } s\text{-}\kappa\text{-column symmetric.}
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.3: Let $P \in F_n$, $Z \in P\{1,2,4\}$, $C((KVP)^T) = C(KVZ)$. Then P is $s\text{-}\kappa\text{-CS NFM} \Leftrightarrow Z$ is $s\text{-}\kappa\text{-CS NFM}$.

Proof: Given $Z \in P\{1, 2, 4\}$,

$$PZP = P, ZPZ = Z, (ZP)^T = ZP$$

$$\begin{aligned} C(KVP) &= C(P) && \text{[Preliminary 2.1]} \\ &= C(ZP) && [ZPZ = Z, PZP = P] = N((ZP)^T) [(ZP)^T = ZP] \\ &= C(P^T Z^T) \\ &= C(Z^T) \\ &= C((KVZ)^T). && \text{[Preliminary 2.1]} \end{aligned}$$

$$KVP \text{ is column symmetric NFM} \Leftrightarrow C(KVP) = C((KVP)^T)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow C((KVZ)^T) = C(KVZ)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow KVZ \text{ is CS NFM}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow Z \text{ is } s\text{-}\kappa\text{-CS NFM.}$$

4. Conclusion:

Firstly, we present equivalent characterizations of an k -CS, CS, s -CS, s - k CS NFM. Also, we give the example of s - k -symmetric NFM is s - k -CS Neutrosophic fuzzy matrix the opposite isn't always true. We discussed various generalized inverses of NFM and generalized inverses of an s - k CS P corresponding to the sets $P\{1, 2\}$, $P\{1, 2, 3\}$ and $P\{1, 2, 4\}$ are characterized. Finally, to conclude we have introduced the concept of secondary k -CS neutrosophic fuzzy matrices. In future we will work on interval valued secondary k -CS neutrosophic fuzzy matrices.

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